

THE ASSUAN DAM

ON the 23rd December last His Highness the Khedive performed the ceremony of opening the Assuan Dam extension works, which are likely to give a great impetus to the progress and prosperity of Egypt. It is scarcely necessary to recall that the Dam was designed and the site chosen by Sir William Willcocks, and the actual work has been carried out by British engineers and contractors. It was in 1883 that Sir Colin Scott-Moncrieff, then responsible for Egyptian irrigation, obtained as his assistant Mr. Willcocks, but it was not till 1889 that the question of the suitability of various proposed sites for the Dam were fully considered. The formal report that Assuan met all the requirements was made in 1893 and 1894, but no progress could be made pending the solution of the financial difficulty. This was not finally solved till Sir Ernest Cassel came forward and provided the funds in 1898. The Dam was completed in 1902 by Sir John Aird and Co., under the direction of Sir B. Baker, and at this time it had a height of 37 metres. In 1904 it became apparent that there was a real necessity to heighten the Dam by 5 metres, and to increase it in thickness by the same number of metres.

In order to avoid risks connected with the difference in temperature between the old and the new portions, the engineers conceived the idea of building the new portion six inches from the old and leaving the former one year by itself so as to become the same temperature as the latter. The space between the two was then filled in, and this was carried out by five grout-mixing machines, specially designed for the purpose at the works of Sir John Aird and Co. Here cement and water, or grout, was mixed in the top of the machine, and

[Photo by H. d'Egville.]

ONE OF THE FAMOUS GROUT-MIXING MACHINES WHICH WERE SPECIALLY DESIGNED TO FILL IN THE CEMENT AND WATER UNITING THE NEW PORTION OF THE ASSUAN DAM TO THE OLD.

[Photo by H. d'Egville.]

ONE OF THE LOCK GATES AT THE ASSUAN DAM.

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carried down by means of pipes to the foundation, and so gradually to the top of the Dam.

By the completion of the Dam, the regular supply of water provided renders unnecessary the employment of the old system of basin irrigation, so that the fields of Egypt can to-day be cultivated all the year round free from drought at low-Nile or submersion at flood time. The extension works have cost £E1,500,000, and at the interesting ceremony of opening them, in which the Khedive and Lord Kitchener took part, a message of congratulation was read from His Majesty King George, who truly referred to the work as "a vast undertaking which will confer far-reaching benefits on landowners, and especially on poorer cultivators."

H. D.